

ISic2742

I.Sicily inscription 2742

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ⲡ(Χρίστο)ς αὐτῆ
2. Σωφρώνια
3. ἀπεγέναιτο
4. τριάντα πέν τε αἰτῶν

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1893

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644840

PHI 333248

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 45.1416

Curbera, J.B. 1995. Two christian inscriptions from Sicily. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 108: 100-101. At 100 no.1

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 291 no.52

Wessel, C. 1989. *Inscriptiones Graecae Christianae Veteres Occidentis*.
Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae. Bari. At 684

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.
Vatican. At no.20

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